

highest rice yield (1.7 t/ha) was with ICPL 138; the lowest with ICPL 186 (1.0 t/ha). Rice yields from the intercrop were 22-57% less than yields of rice alone.

Pigeonpea yields in the intercropped plots were 2-62% less than in the monocrop. The most compatible rice - pigeonpea combination featured ICPL 295 (56% yield advantage). □

Rice-based cropping systems for optimum production under resource constraints

S. K. Uttaray, P. K. Mahapatra, G. K. Patro, and R. N. Patnaik, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 3, Orissa, India

During 1979-81, rice variety Jajati (135 d duration) was grown during the wet season with 80-18-33 kg NPK/ha.

Wheat variety Sonalika (95 d duration), mungbean variety Sujata (70 d), and peanut variety AK12-24 (120 d) were grown after rice in the dry season at 3 moisture regimes (1, 3, and 5 irrigations to wheat; 1, 2, and 3 irrigations to mungbean; 1, 3, and 4 irrigations to peanut). Three fertility levels (level 1 = 120-26-50 kg NPK/ha for wheat; 20-18-33 kg NPK/ha for mungbean and peanut; level 2 = 2/3 of level 1; level 3 = 1/3 of level 1) were tested in a split-plot design with three replications.

Rice was transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing; wheat and mungbean were sown at 20 × 5 cm; peanut was sown at 30 × 10 cm. The soil was an acidic Latosol, sandy loam texture, with pH 5.9, EC 0.233 dS/m, 0.457% organic C, 0.04% total N, 66.6 kg available P/ha, and 300 kg available K/ha.

Rice yield was low in 1980 because of gall midge attack. Mean total yield was highest from rice - peanut (4.3 t/ha) followed by rice - wheat (3.0 t/ha) (Table 1). Rice - peanut also yielded more protein, carbohydrate, and energy.

Yields of wheat and peanut increased with increasing irrigation; mungbean yields decreased after two irrigations. As

Table 1. Efficiency of cropping system under limited irrigation and fertilizer supply.^a Bhubaneswar, India, 1979-81.

Cropping system	Yield (t/ha)				Protein ^b (t/ha)	Carbohydrate (t/ha)	Energy (MJ × 10 ³ /ha)
	1979	1980	1981	Mean			
Rice - wheat	3.1 (1.1)	1.1 (1.0)	1.9 (0.8)	2.0 (1.0)	0.2	1.7	33.4
Rice - mungbean	3.1 (0.4)	1.2 (0.5)	2.0 (0.5)	2.1 (0.5)	0.2	1.4	27.1
Rice - peanut	3.1 (2.2)	1.2 (1.8)	2.3 (2.3)	2.2 (2.1)	0.5	1.6	57.4

^a Figures in parentheses indicate the dry season crop yield. ^b Protein, carbohydrate, and energy calculated for edible portions only as per standards fixed by the National Institute of Nutrition (ICMR), Hyderabad, India.

Table 2. Effect of irrigation and fertility level (F1, 2, 3) on grain yield of wheat, mungbean, and peanut grown after rice.^a Bhubaneswar, India, 1979-81.

Number of irrigation	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	F1	F2	F3	Mean	
	Wheat				
1 (I1)	1.03	0.80	0.64	0.82	
3 (I2)	1.32	1.09	0.63	1.01	
5 (I3)	1.31	1.06	0.84	1.07	
Mean	1.22	0.98	0.70	0.97	
	Mungbean				
1 (I1)	0.36	0.43	0.41	0.40	
2 (I2)	0.66	0.46	0.42	0.51	
3 (I3)	0.55	0.46	0.35	0.45	
Mean	0.52	0.45	0.39	0.45	
	Peanut				
1 (I1)	1.95	1.75	1.40	1.70	
3 (I2)	2.64	2.33	1.78	2.25	
4 (I3)	2.60	2.51	2.12	2.41	
Mean	2.40	2.20	1.17	2.12	
LSD (0.05)	Wheat		Mungbean		Peanut
I	0.10		0.04		0.05
F	0.04		0.03		0.04
F×I	0.09		0.05		0.08
I×F	0.12		0.06		0.08
CV (%)	Wheat		Mungbean		Peanut
I	10		10		3
F	7		9		3

^aF×I = LSD of 2 submeans at the same level of main. I×F = LSD of 2 main means at same level of different levels of sub. CV (%) I = CV of main plot, F = CV of subplots.

fertility level decreased yield of all crops was reduced.

The interactions were significant at all

levels of irrigation and fertility (Table 2). The best responses were with mid-level irrigation and high fertility. □

ERRATA

IRRN 12:5 (Oct 1987) Performance of improved rice varieties in farmers' fields in Bhutan, by N. Q. R. Nathaniels, et al. In the table (p. 5), the site mean yield for

Techuzamba, Wangdiphodrang, should read 6.7 t/ha (not 3.3 t/ha).

IRRN 125 (Oct 1987) p. 37. Chemical analyses and thermal studies of azolla. The first author's name should read M. L. Aldema. □